

Navigating the Unknown: Journey of Transferee Teachers in Adjusting to the New School Community

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Abstract. This study explored the experiences of transferee teachers as they move through the challenging process of integrating into a new school. In-depth interviews and reflective observations are combined with a qualitative research design in this study to collect rich, nuanced data from a broad sample of transfer teachers. The study aims to comprehend the various difficulties, coping strategies, and final adjustment of these teachers in the strange setting of an alternative school. The research highlights typical difficulties encountered in the first stage, such as getting used to new administrative practices, adapting to the school's own culture, and forming professional connections with both students and colleagues. Additionally, the study explores the coping mechanisms transfer teachers employed to overcome these obstacles, including looking for mentorship, taking advantage of professional development opportunities, and using technology to communicate and share resources. Successful integration is primarily dependent on several factors, including ongoing professional development, active participation in extracurricular activities, and long-term partnerships. The results have ramifications for educators, legislators, and school administrators since they provide suggestions for creating a more encouraging work environment for transfer instructors, ultimately increasing their efficacy in the classroom and overall job satisfaction.

KEY WORDS

1. navigating the unknown 2. transferee teachers 3. new school community

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1. Introduction

The transferee teachers' adjustment to the new school community was very challenging, both in terms of work tasks (physical) and mixed emotional feelings toward new co-teachers. Working at a school for the first time can be exciting and overwhelming if the teachers are new teachers. Meeting and building relationships with other educators, students, and parents takes time when entering a new school environment. The culture of the school serving has been formed over many years, and it can take time to adjust and acclimate to it. At first, a school's culture may be challenging to identify, but new transfer teachers will begin to see and feel it over time. In general, an organization's culture is "the way we do things around here." In contrast, school climate is "the way we feel around here," which is a perception that can change from day to day. From a global perspective, Khan (2018) pointed out that all humans have a fundamental need for and right to education. It is essential in guiding

society in a favorable direction and setting it on the path to progress. Not only are the curriculum, teaching methods, and atmosphere important for imparting great education, but qualified, trustworthy, and committed teachers also play a crucial role. Any learning program cannot function without a teacher whose presence ensures the curriculum's success. According to researchers and school officials, nothing influences learners' success more than the caliber of the teachers (Noor, Ishaque, Memon, Lodhi, 2018). The current educational environment is constantly changing due to the combination of external and internal factors that influence the field of education. Particularly in a school with a negative environment, this can affect teachers' quality of teaching. It may cause teachers to experience stress, tension, and discontent at school. In such a situation, there is no need for the teacher to work effectively. This prompts public school teachers to traverse complex challenges and seek new opportunities. Therefore, teachers may need to seek transfer to other schools. Transferring from one school to another is one of the crucial aspects in the journey of professionalism, a process known as teacher transfer. The transitioning of the teachers into new school community is a critical stage that affects their efficiency, well-being and conclusively, the quality of education given to the students. Transferring a teacher can happen for a number of reasons, including organizational, professional, or personal ones. It is a widespread occurrence in education and has significant ramifications for both the teachers and the educational institutions involved (Ingersoll, , Strong, 2018). For instance, for their professional development, teachers frequently switch schools. It comes from a desire to grow professionally and take on harder duties and responsibilities. Teachers may search for transfer opportunities to advance their careers or take on new professional challenges - changing occupations to become a department head, curriculum coordinator, or school administrator from being a classroom teacher. Due to a variety of reasons, including leadership chances, opportunities for professional development and growth, relationships with other professionals in the field, and a variety of teaching experiences, career advancement has a substantial impact on teachers' decisions to transfer (Ronfeldt, Loeb, Wyckoff, 2021). In addition, many teachers face financial problems. Financial consideration is needed in any working environment. Long commutes could result in more expensive transportation. Teachers can save money on fuel or public transportation costs by moving to a school closer to their homes. Aside from saving time and money, moving closer to home could build community connections. Teaching in the same area where one resides can foster a stronger feeling of community and investment in the local town's and its citizens' welfare (Bonetti, Pietrobelli, 2019). Furthermore, teachers thinking about their long-term career paths may consider living close to their families as part of their intentions to settle down and grow roots in a particular place. (Johnson, Birkeland , Peske, 2008). Transfers may also occur due to situations involving the teacher's family, such as taking care of a sick member or being assigned to a school in the area where the student's family resides. Personal factors like a spouse's job transfer, dual-teaching families, family stability and well-being, and social support can all contribute to teacher transfers. If a teacher wants to be closer to their family or if their family's situation has changed, they might ask to be transferred. Transfers are made, especially for female instructors, to address family-related issues. The time spent getting to and from school has an impact on their marriage, kids, and commitments (Kulgami S. 2023). However, transitioning to different school may encounter a lot of challenges. Teachers who transfer to a new district must make an effort to adjust to their new working conditions, which include a variety

of elements. Their expectations from the administration, school board, and other people in the district might be different or new. The number of students or peers that teachers interact with could change. The optimum seating arrangement, accessible materials, the evolving curriculum, and the classroom management system are just a few of the things that kids will need to get acclimated to in a new classroom. Additionally, without prior acquaintance, it can be difficult to interact with parents and adequately inform them about their child's development and school activities. Considering that parents have a significant impact on both the growth of their children and the success of the overall educational system, it is crucial to be familiar with them and open to their cultural practices. Also, transfers may not be done for teachers' reasons but it is also to address to distribute evenly the workforce in the Department of Education. Based on the Teacher Deployment in the Basic Education Information System (BEIS), uneven distribution of teachers in public schools is consistently shown by analysis of prior academic years. While there are still a significant number of "cool colored" schools—those with a student-to-teacher ratio of less than 40: 1, there are also still a significant number of "red" and "black" schools. Therefore, in order for the Department of Education (DepEd) to guarantee the equity of teacher deployment, teacher transfers from one station to another are essential. It's significant to remember that school districts and educational authorities in Binugao District, Davao City, should adhere to the specific rules and procedures that apply to teacher transitions, ensuring fairness and openness; transfers should often be performed through a formal process. When applying for transfers, teachers should weigh a variety of criteria that are in line with their professional objectives and personal circumstances when deciding to move to a new location. Due to its possible effects on teacher retention, job satisfaction, and overall educational outcomes, teacher transfer has received more attention from scholars, politicians, and educators. However, the adjustment experience of transferee teachers in the context of public schools continues to be a neglected field of research despite its significance. It was in this challenging situation that this study was conducted to determine the lived experiences and the adaptation techniques of the transferee teachers in their new school community in the Division of Davao City.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This study aimed to illuminate transferee teachers' experiences transitioning to a new school setting and pinpoint the elements that help or hinder a smooth transition. With this, policymakers and educational leaders can create tailored support plans for teachers when such situations arise, thereby increasing professional growth, fostering a healthy school climate, and promoting teacher well-being.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aims to explore the insights and experiences of transferee teachers in adjusting to their new school community. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the main challenges faced by transferee teachers during their adjustment to a new school community?
- (2) How do the transferee teachers cope with the trials encountered in teaching in a new environment?
- (3) What are the realizations learned from the experiences of transferee teachers in public schools?

1.3. Definition of Terms—

The following were terms used to make the study more comprehensive: Teacher Transfer - also known as teacher mobility or teacher reassignment, was defined as the process of moving a teacher from one school or educational institution to another within the same school district Career Advancement was defined as the process of progressing professionally and accepting more challenging assignments and responsibilities. It is a process that an individual may undergo to evolve their occupational status. It is the process of making decisions for long-term learning to align personal needs of physical or psychological fulfillment with career advancement opportunities. Proximity to Home – relocating to schools closer to homes that could provide convenience, comfortability with the environment, and ease of transport

Family Reasons - transfers may also occur due to family-related circumstances, such as caring for a sick relative, spouse's employment transfer, building a family, pregnancy, and children needing immediate or special care. Cultural Adjustment – the process of adapting to the cultural norms, values, and practices in the new school community, which would lead people to be comfortable, well, and successful in their unfamiliar environment. Student diversity - refers to the presence of a wide range of differences among students in terms of race, ethnicity, language, gender, and socioeconomic status in the educational setting Establishing a Relationship – refers to the process of creating connections, bonds, or associations between individuals based on mutual understanding, trust, communication, and shared experiences

1.4. Significant of the Study—By examining these questions, researchers could learn a lot about the difficulties, coping mechanisms, and support networks that affect transferee teachers' effective integration into their new professional setting. The research findings can influence educational practices and policies that encourage a welcoming and encouraging environment for teachers as they adjust to a new school environment. Furthermore, this study attempts to offer a thorough and nuanced knowledge of transferee teachers' journeys as they settle into new school settings. The research would add to the body of knowledge on teacher mobility, influence evidence-based strategies, and help educational leaders develop welcoming cultures that promote transferee teachers' well-being and professional development. Therefore, this study would be significant to the following: Department of Education Officials. The DepEd officials, particularly in the Division of Davao City, would continue supporting teachers in their new environment and providing assistance to solve the educational challenges encountered by the

teachers. Certain policies and projects may also be created and initiated to maximize the support given to the learners and teachers. The Local Government Unit/Barangay Officials. Government officials, especially the barangay officials of Davao City, continually extend their helping hands to build stronger community linkages and help teachers address the educational challenges they encounter in their new school community. Teachers. This study's findings would benefit the transferee teachers in their new school community, as the participants share their challenges and solutions to overcome those challenges. Parents. This study would provide insights into teachers' challenges when teaching their children. This would give them a sense of understanding and may help build a stronger partnership and cooperation between teachers and parents, making the teaching and learning process more effective. Learners. This study would provide insights into how their teachers were performing their expected tasks and what was expected of them. It would also unravel the lived experiences and challenges faced in

teaching in rural elementary schools. Future researchers. Future researchers should consider some other aspects of the transferee teachers' experiences in their new school community not

1.5. Theoretical Lens—Social Identity Theory, developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner in the 1970s, provides a useful theoretical framework for understanding the adjustment of transfer teachers in a new school community. This theory focuses on how individuals develop a sense of belonging and self-concept based on the groups they identify with. When applied to transferee teachers, Social Identity Theory can offer insights into their adjustment process within the new school environment. The Cognitive Dissonance Theory, proposed by Leon Festinger, will also be applied in this investigation. It suggests that individuals experience discomfort when they hold contradictory beliefs or attitudes. When applied to transferee teachers, this might mean they experience cognitive dissonance between their previous teaching methods and the new school's expectations. This discomfort could motivate them to adapt their teaching practices to align with the new environment, ultimately reducing the dissonance and promoting better adjustment. Ecological Systems Theory will be used in this study. This was developed by Urie Bronfenbrenner. It emphasizes the influence of various systems (microsystem, mesosystem, exosystem, macrosystem, and chronosystem) on an individual's development and behavior. Transferee teachers' adjustment can be viewed through this lens by considering factors such as their interactions with students, colleagues, administrators, and the broader educational context. This theory highlights the interconnectedness of these systems and how

covered in this research. Other subject areas pertaining to this study may be conducted in other grade levels and districts to obtain a better comparison of the phenomenon being explored.

they impact the adjustment process. The last theory that will be used in this study is stress and coping theories. Various stress and coping theories, such as Lazarus and Folkman's Transactional Model of Stress and Coping, emphasize how individuals perceive and respond to stressors. Transferee teachers may encounter stressors related to adjusting to a new curriculum, classroom dynamics, and school culture. Their coping strategies, such as seeking social support, problem-solving, or emotional regulation, can impact their adjustment process. Each of these theories provides a unique perspective on the adjustment of transferee teachers in a new school community. Combining insights from multiple theories can offer a comprehensive understanding of the complex process that these teachers go through as they transition and integrate into a new educational environment. This theoretical framework can be viewed as a way to provide an enhanced practical application by offering an understanding of what to expect in adjusting to a new school community. These three ideas have made significant contributions to both the teaching-learning process and the development of the educational system, notably in the area of science. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study. Based on the figure, there were two interconnected working themes. These themes were the challenges encountered by the transferee teachers in adjusting to the new school community, the adaptive techniques of the transferee teachers in the new school community, and insights learned from the experiences of the informants.

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

2. Methodology

This chapter covered the method, research subjects, data collection, role of the researcher, data analysis, validity of the study, and ethical considerations. The ensuing design and implementation, as described in this chapter, were necessary for exploring facts and knowledge in this investigation. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation was appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups effectively elicit data on a group’s cultural norms and generate broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—Certain assumptions and beliefs were always carried into any labor or study. Qualitative researchers regularly wrote about their theories and beliefs in their research because they recognized how important they were to their job. The philosophical presumption served as a framework for gathering, analyzing, and interpreting the facts in a particular field of research. To comprehend the significance of these presumptions to our study, we explained them and placed them within interpretive frameworks. It created the context for the forthcoming judgments and choices. The sorts of philosophical presumptions were numerous and were discussed below. Epistemology. Researchers made an effort to get as close as they could to the study subjects. Subjective evidence was compiled based on individual perspectives from field research. This speaks to comprehending how knowledge claims are supported by maintaining close contact with participants throughout the study to gather first-hand data (Henschke, 2014). According to BK Hofer (2001), the researcher should close the gap with the participants to foster collaboration, become an insider, and spend time in the field

with them. The researcher should develop a close relationship with the participants to get direct information that adds to the study's knowledge. Ontology, often known as the nature of reality, was concerned with reality and its properties. Researchers incorporate the concept of numerous realities and report on these multiple realities by examining complicated evidence derived from the experiences and views of various people. This research section focuses on how it connects to the nature of reality (Ahmed, 2008). Additionally, it was a branch of metaphysics that was interested in defining the categories of genuinely real things. Creswell (2012) claims that participants in the research circumstance created the reality. Participants in the study must describe it as subjective and multifaceted. Multiple realities exist, including that of the researcher, the people who were studied, and the reader or audience who were interpreting the study. The researcher centered on the participants' interpretations, opinions, and voices in this study through numerous quotes and themes that reflected the words and provided proof of many viewpoints to develop and construct the distinctness and commonality of reactions. The study's participants' responses were coded and examined. Additionally, the researcher carefully coded the respondents' responses to guarantee the validity of the results. This prevented the development of personal bias during the study and supported the sincerity and consideration of the responses. Rhetoric was nothing more than the participants' descriptions of reality. This was crucial since it indicated that the researcher had to report fairly what they had seen and heard from the participants. In addition, the researcher would substitute the terms credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability for objectivity and internal and external validity. Axiology, or the significance of values of research. Researchers will explicitly state their values in the study and deliberately disclose their biases, as well as the value-laden character of the data they collected on the ground. According to axiology, the researcher should communicate the narrative's guiding principles openly and include both their own and participants' interpretations (Carnaghan, 2019). As a result, it was also known as the theory of value, the philosophical study of goodness or value in the broadest sense. The researcher was aware of how sensitive and value-laden the study's information was. As a result, the researcher carefully analyzed the replies in light of the participants' individual interpretations while maintaining the validity of the participants' responses. This was done to preserve the honor and worth of each piece of data collected from the participants. The researcher used qualitative phenomenological research methodology, which enables the examination of the teachers' experiences teaching in rural schools and reveals their thoughts and feelings regarding these experiences. In line Dm Barrow (2017) found that phenomenological research allows participants to investigate their own experiences, various abstract perceptions of the study phenomenon, as well as their sensory impressions of the phenomenon. As a result, the study's methodology was based on either your own or other people's sensory perceptions and experiences. The purpose of the study is to describe and analyze the phenomenon utilizing the experiences of other people in order to develop in-depth information about the phenomenon. The objective of this study, which is to comprehend teachers' experiences when instructing in a physically remote classroom, fits well with the criteria. Phenomenological research would examine the lived experiences of teachers to discover meaning that may or may not be known to the individual who experienced it and to characterize the phenomenon through a composite narrative.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions—*

The method was distinct from the methodology. While "method" refers to precise knowledge and technique, "methodology" refers to a creative and responsive way of understanding problems and subject matter (Gerodias, 2013). This study revealed teachers' first-hand accounts of transferring to other schools, particularly those teachers from the Division of Davao City. The researcher's desire to understand the underlying meaning of the difficulties faced by the teachers in adjusting to a new school community would serve as the impetus for conducting qualitative research, which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited by Gerodias (2013), considered useful in locating "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena. This need was thought to be met by utilizing phenomenology to portray the instructors' stories in such a way that, as David (2005) said, the themes, symbols, and significance of the experiences were presented. The foundation of phenomenological research is two premises. The first is that knowledge

can be gained legitimately, richly, and fruitfully from experience. As noted by Morrissey and Higgs (2006), Becker (1992) asserts that experience is a source of knowledge and changes one's behavior. According to the definition, human experience was not seen as an unreliable source of information but rather as the foundation of knowledge about human events. The second premise of phenomenological research is the idea that the everyday world was a rich and fruitful source of information and that by examining how an event occurs in our daily lives, we can gain important insights into its nature and learn a lot about ourselves (Morrissey Higgs, 2006). The researcher anticipated that by using phenomenology, which is concerned with the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the teachers' subjective experiences, difficulties, and coping mechanisms in adjusting to a new school community would be explored. Insights would then be drawn as the basis for potential future research and policy analysis related to this research.

2.3. Design and Procedure—The research methodology to be used in this study is qualitative, specifically a phenomenological research design. Creswell (2012) defined phenomenology as a qualitative research methodology that emphasizes the shared nature of life experiences within a given group. To arrive at a description of the nature of the specific phenomenon was the approach's main objective. Interviews were typically performed with a group of people who had first-hand knowledge of an occasion, circumstance, or experience. In addition, information from records, observations, and art was employed. The information was then examined and reread to identify themes and words that may be categorized according to their meanings. Through this method, the researcher could develop the event, circumstance, or experience's universal significance, which would

lead to a deeper comprehension of the phenomena. Additionally, Maxwell (2013) added that phenomenology, which has roots in philosophy, psychology, and education, aims to extract the most honest, unadulterated data. In some interpretations of the methodology, the researcher would use bracketing to record personal interactions with the subject to aid in detachment. The act of taking notes was one way to bracket. According to Corbetta (2003), the phenomenological research design is a qualitative style of research in which interviews are used as an in-depth method that can provide deep knowledge and explanations and aid in understanding the perspectives of the subjects. Additionally, according to Creswell (2012), interviews are most often conducted as part of qualitative research and take place when researchers ask one or more participants broad, open-ended ques-

tions and record their responses. Audio tapes were frequently used to enable more accurate transcribing. Interviews were helpful for checking in with specific respondents after questionnaires, for example, to learn more about their responses. Interviews were employed in qualitative research to explore the significance of major topics in the subjects' lives. The major goal of conducting interviews was to understand what the respondents would say (McNamara, 1999). In addition, according to Quad's (2016) assertions, the researcher would write the data into a computer file and then transcribe it in order to examine it after the interviews. In-depth research on a topic and learning the background of a participant's experiences. Then, the researcher would gather information from people who had firsthand knowledge of the topic under examination, usually through in-depth interviews. Next, the data analysis would involve triangulation, which takes the transcribed interviews and extracts important remarks from them. The significant statements would be organized into meaning clusters based on how each one would fit into a certain psychological or phenomenological idea. The textural description of what was experienced and the structural description of how it was experienced were brought together to create

an overall description of the experience. The researcher would incorporate his or her individual interpretation of the events. Finally, the report was created to help readers better understand the fundamental, unchanging structure of the experience. On the other hand, there would be a number of difficulties. The researcher would need a firm foundation in phenomenological philosophical principles. The study's subjects were chosen from among people who had firsthand knowledge of the occurrence. It would be challenging for the researcher to set aside personal experiences and observations. Additionally, the researcher would have to decide how and when to include personal observations in the study. Phenomenological approaches highlight the value of personal perspective and interpretation and were founded on the epistemological paradigm of personal knowledge and subjectivity. As a result, they were effective instruments for comprehending subjective experience, gaining insights into people's motivations and behaviors, and dispelling the mass of widely held beliefs and presumptions. The researcher would use phenomenology as a qualitative method because the goal of this study is to examine and evaluate the teacher's experience and sentiments regarding teaching in rural schools.

2.4. Research Participants—Transferee teachers in the public schools in Binugao District, Division of Davao City, would serve as the study's primary informants. The researcher utilized at least ten elementary teachers chosen at random from the schools as qualitative participants for virtual in-depth interviews (IDI). The informants were elementary teachers working in the Binugao District's various schools for the Department of Education for no more than three

years. The researcher would utilize the purposive sampling design since the participants were chosen based on the criteria or purpose of the study. This method is also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling. The selection of the participants was purposefully done to ensure that the findings would be authentic (Marshall, 1996). The criteria for choosing the participants are elementary teachers and transferees for school years 2022-2023.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—This research project has incorporated the Belmont

Report published by the National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of

Biomedical and Behavioral Research in 1979. In which it has identified the three basic ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice as the framework for addressing ethical issues arising from the conduct of research with human subjects. In this field study, the researcher must take into account a number of ethical concerns about the research participant. It was possible to name ethical considerations as one of the research's most crucial components. The researcher must uphold and support the goals of the study, which include disseminating accurate information, telling the truth, and avoiding mistakes. Informed Consent. The Treaty Principle of Participation, as cited by McLeod (2009), shall be followed in the conduct and application of this study. The participants were invited, which would guarantee that their involvement in the study was entirely voluntary and predicated on a thorough knowledge of the relevant material. The study's appendices contain information on the selection and recruiting of participants. To conduct phenomenological research and conduct an informed, moral, academic inquiry, it was essential to gain the trust and cooperation of research participants (Walker, 2007, as cited by Pillerin, 2012). Before the interviews were scheduled and they took part in the phenomenological research procedure, all participants were given an informed permission form. A personal acceptance, agreement, and release indicating a willingness to participate in the study must all be signed by each participant. The informed consent letter's objectives include introducing the research project, giving contact information, outlining the study's aim, asking recipients to voluntarily participate, and outlining the data the informants were expected to contribute. Before taking part in the study, each participant must sign the letter of consent and send it back to the researcher. Vulnerability of Research Participants. Since all of the participants in this study are qualified instructors working in public schools, they were all allowed to respond to the research questionnaire. As a result, the researcher would reassure them that they may contact him or her at the provided phone number and address if they have any concerns or need further explanation on the study. Risks, Benefits, and Safety. The respondents were recruited free of coercion, undue influence, or inducement. Moreover, respondents were provided with the contact numbers of the chair of the panel or panel members in case they had queries related to the study. This was done to answer possible questions of the respondents. Furthermore, in the event that respondents experienced discomfort and inconvenience while answering the questions, they were not compelled to participate in any manner. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were safe during the survey and interview. Thus, the distribution of the questionnaire was conducted in a safe venue and administered at their convenient time. The dominant concern of this study was the Treaty Principle of Protection, as reflected in the respect for the rights of privacy and confidentiality and the minimization of risk. This would be done by assigning pseudonyms for each informant so as not to disclose their identity. The possibility of a degree of risk inherent to this was minimized by taking all reasonable steps to guarantee participant confidentiality. Privacy and Confidentiality of Information. The Data Privacy Act of 2002 was followed in this study to ensure that participant names were protected and that the data could not be traced back to its original sources. Therefore, the data sources' anonymity was ensured with the utmost care. As a result, any written results from this study were kept confidential. Additionally, every issue can be taken into account to ensure that there is no conflict of interest between the researcher and the respondents. Avoiding false information of any kind and biased reporting of primary data findings were both important. Justice. The researchers' jobs and respective

roles during data collection were explained to the respondents. They were informed that they must answer the survey questions honestly and completely. Additionally, all communications pertaining to the research should be open and truthful. In a similar vein, they were told that they were the study's first-round beneficiaries. Transparency. The respondents and the administrators of the participating schools would have access to the study's findings since they were stored on a CD or another type of storage device and were available upon request to the researcher. Additionally, by studying the study's findings. Each participant would also be informed that they could request and be given permission to check their individual transcript after the interview has been conducted and that they had the right to withdraw their information at any point up until the data collection process was complete. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend, or remove any information which they feel might identify them. The researcher reserved the right to employ the use of pseudonyms, and changing names and or non-significant dates in the interest of the protection of the identity of the participant in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher would make sure that they were properly qualified to carry out the study. Prior to writing the thesis, which was the last step in earning a master's degree, the researcher had to complete the academic requirements, pass the comprehensive examination, and demonstrate their suitability to conduct the study in terms of

their physical, mental, emotional, and financial capabilities. The advisee-adviser combination would also guarantee that the study was completed. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher would work to ensure that the study can be finished successfully by the deadline and that they have the required tools. The technical committee would also aid in improving the paper by providing the necessary recommendations and suggestions for enhancing the study. The researcher also makes sure they have the money to carry out and complete the investigation. Thus, it was hoped that this investigation would be finished by the deadline. Community Involvement. The researcher would respect local customs, cultures, and respondents' points of view throughout this study. Additionally, this study would not use any form of deception in any aspect of its execution, including participant recruitment and data collection techniques. Additionally, the researcher must convey their sincere gratitude for the interview subjects' enthusiastic participation in the study's execution. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher would respect other authors' works by giving correct credit to them and rephrasing what they have expressed in their own words. To show that text has been borrowed from another publication, the researcher would always use quotation marks. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty is there when working on the article and that no deliberate distortion, making up of data or results, or purposeful putting forth of inaccurate conclusions would be present.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The role of the researcher in this study was to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes, the experiences being explored were fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other occasions,

reliving past experiences may be difficult. However, the data were being collected, and the primary responsibility of the researcher was to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. *Data Collection*—Ensured educational continuity involves a systematic process that adheres to ethical considerations and research principles. The following were the steps for gathering the needed data. Asking permission from the Schools Division Superintendent. The researcher would be asked for permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study in the identified school. The researcher would send a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent with Chapters 1 and 2 attached, together with the research instrument explaining the study's objectives and identifying the participants. The researcher would wait for the SDS's response before conducting the study. Asking permission from the school heads. After securing the approval of the SDS, the researcher would send letters to the principals of the schools explaining the study to be conducted in their schools. Obtaining consent from the participants. The researcher would ask permission from the participants and their parents/guardians. They would be formally oriented about the study and the process they would go through as participants. Conducting

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, thematic analysis was utilized to analyze the gathered data. The researcher would analyze the participants' answers from the interviews using Creswell's Model, specifically the identifying of themes approach. According to Creswell (2012), themes in qualitative research are similar codes aggregated together to form a major idea in the database. Familiarization with the data was common to all forms of qualitative analysis; the researcher would immerse herself in, and become intimately familiar with, their data, reading and re-reading the data and noting any initial analytic observations. Coding was also a common element of many approaches to qualitative analysis, involving generating pithy

the interview. The researcher conducted the in-depth interview using the interview questionnaire. The profile of the participants was taking notes and jotting down, and conversations were recorded using a sound recorder for ease of transcription. The researcher carefully listened and responded actively during the interviews. Transcribing the responses of the interviewees. The researcher would transcribe the responses of the interviewees precisely by recalling their answers from the sound recorder. Since the participants would use their vernacular language, the researcher would translate it to English language. Data Coding and thematizing. After the transcription, the data would be categorized and coded. Then, themes were extracted, and individual data within the participants were compared and contrasted. The researcher would then conduct a second round of interviews (FGD) to corroborate any data that needed further explanation and input from the participants. Additional information was gathered and examined thoroughly and integrated into the existing body of data. After this, data were compared and contrasted between the participants to develop patterns and trends.

labels for important features of the data of relevance to the (broad) research question guiding the analysis. Coding was not simply a method of data reduction; it was also an analytic process, so codes capture both a semantic and conceptual reading of the data. The researcher coded every data item and ended this phase by collating all their codes and relevant data extracts. Searching for themes was a coherent and meaningful pattern in the data relevant to the research question. The researcher ended this phase by collating all the coded data relevant to each theme. Reviewing themes. The researcher would reflect on whether the themes tell a convincing and compelling story about the data and begin to define the nature of each individual theme and the re-

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

relationship between the themes. Defining and naming themes: The researcher would prepare a detailed analysis of each theme, identifying the ‘essence’ of each theme and constructing a concise, punchy, and informative name for each

theme. Writing up involves weaving together the analytic narrative and data extracts to tell the reader a coherent and persuasive story about the data and contextualizing it concerning existing literature.

2.9. *Framework of Analysis*—The framework analysis of this research would utilize Colaizzi’s method of 1978, which was a rigorous and robust qualitative method that the researchers used to find, understand, describe, and depict the experiences of persons as they experience them. This method also revealed emergent themes and their interwoven relationship. This method aims to uncover the genuine experience of the phenomenon under investiga-

tion. Colaizzi’s method consists of seven steps. First, informants’ experiences were read to understand the whole. Then, significant statements were extracted, and meanings were formulated from them. The meanings were organized into themes and integrated into an exhaustive description. Next, the essential structure of the phenomenon was formulated. Finally, for validation, the informants evaluated the analysis result to see if it was the same as their original experiences (Turunen et al. 1994).

2.10. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—The concepts of validity and reliability were rela-

tively foreign to the field of qualitative research. Qualitative researchers substitute data trustwor-

thiness instead of focusing on reliability and validity. Trustworthiness consists of components such as credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). By observing the attributes of prolonged engagement, credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data. To address the issue of credibility, the researcher interviews as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Credibility refers to the extent to which a research account is believable and appropriate, with particular reference to the level of agreement between participants and the researcher. The notion of credibility was most often associated with the framework presented by Yvonna Lincoln and Egon Guba. Transferability was the degree to which the results of qualitative re-

search could be transferred to other contexts or settings with other respondents. The researcher facilitates the transferability judgment by a potential user through thick description. Dependability was the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and ensure that the findings were consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate your study, they should have enough information from the research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. Conformability refers to the objectivity of research during data collection and data analysis. There needs to be congruency between two or more independent persons about the accuracy, relevance, or meaning of the data (Polit Beck, 2012). Conformability also indicates a means to demonstrate quality.

3. Results and Discussion

This section provides the generated results from the analysis of the interviews conducted. The analysis of their interviews presents themes with comprehensive discussions that answer the study's objectives. All subjects are public school elementary transfer teachers. Each subject differed in their years of experience, ranging from first-year teachers to having more than thirty years of experience. A brief profile of the subject is provided, and they were assigned pseudonyms to protect their anonymity.

3.1. Challenges of Transfer Teachers in Adjusting to a New School Community—Transferring from one school to another is one of the crucial aspects of the journey of professionalism. Transitioning the teachers into the new school community is a critical stage that affects their efficiency, well-being, and, conclusively, the quality of education given to the students. Transferring a teacher can happen for many reasons, including organizational, professional, or personal. It is a widespread occurrence in education and has important ramifications for both the teachers and the educational institutions involved (Ingersoll, and Strong, 2011). For instance, for the sake of their professional development, teachers frequently switch schools. It comes from a desire to grow professionally

and take on harder duties and responsibilities. Teachers may search for transfer opportunities to advance their careers or take on new professional challenges - changing occupations to become a department head, curriculum coordinator, or school administrator from being a classroom teacher. Due to a variety of reasons, including leadership chances, opportunities for professional development and growth, relationships with other professionals in the field, and a variety of teaching experiences, career advancement has a substantial impact on teachers' decisions to transfer (Ronfeldt, Loeb, and Wyckoff 2013, 2013). The following study analyses the challenges of public-school elementary transfer teachers in adjusting to the new school community.

3.1.1. Cultural Adjustment—Transferred teachers must undergo a cultural adjustment process to fit in with the conventions, values, and practices of their new school community. Teachers who are transferred may run into societal norms, habits, and behaviors that are different from what they are accustomed to. These differences can lead to feeling of uneasiness and uncertainty. Due to this significant differences, teachers commonly experience culture shock. In order to understand culture shock, it is a need to understand culture in the context of school community. The term "culture" refers to the common ideas, standards, customs, attitudes, and ways of doing things that define the social atmosphere and interactions at school. It includes all members of the school community—students, teachers, administrators, staff, parents, and other stakeholders—as well as their collective identities and way of life (Bullivant, 2015). When teachers who experienced different from what they are used to, culture shock may occur. This has long been a topic of academic study (Griffith, Winstanley, Gabriel, 2005). For instance, according to Oberg (1960), "culture shock is precipitated by the anxiety that results from losing all our familiar signs and symbols of social intercourse". Popadiuk Arthur (2004) state that culture shock refers to experiences where one must learn to live with the lack of familiar conventions and get familiar with the new community, typically with the expectation of integrating into the new cultural practices. Culture shock is described as experiences of intense disorientation, confusion, and

3.1.2. Student Differences—Student diversity creates challenges to new transferee teachers with learners (Gay, 2002). Studies show that transferee teachers also face challenges in dealing with classroom management, curriculum planning and implementation, conducting assessments, and workload issues. (Gross-

anxiety experienced when people are immersed into new and unfamiliar cultures with different social conventions, values, and norms" by Griffiths et al. (2005). Therefore, transferee teachers may face big transitions. They must deal with a culture that is distinctively different from the previous schools where they worked (Popadiuk Artur, 2004). However, they might approach this situation differently; some embrace the culture while others reject it (Grimes, 2010). Aside from responding to culture shock, transfer teachers encounter numerous difficulties in adjusting both inside and outside of the four walls of the classroom. The educational system that allows teacher transfer, the school administration and other teachers anticipate them to meet a specific level of performance. Lew and Nelson (2016) assert that, the rapid population growth in several different countries is the cause of the diverse student body. This diverse population frequently presents challenges for transferee teachers in their new school community. Also, transferee teachers may have varying or new expectations from the administration as well as from within the district. In the classroom setting, students will need to get used to a new classroom with new teacher where they will need to figure out the type of teacher they have and the classroom management system. It must also be difficult for the students because that atmosphere where they fostered happiness, support and special memories is different when they have a new teacher. On the other hand, it will be a challenge for the transferee teachers give the same atmosphere (Holmes, Carr Flynn 2017).

man Thompson, 2008; Kyriacou Kunc, 2007; Roehrig, Pressley, Talotta, 2002; Scherff, 2008). One of the critical issue that new teachers encounter dealing with diverse students' cultures, causing the teachers to often overreact to students' due to its adjustment (Irvine Armento, 2001). For example, some students do not par-

ticipate because they are also adjusting to their new teacher. Thus, teachers must be aware that they have built rapport to the student to establish connection, and as a way to get students' attention. Hence, in light of cultural differences, individual cultures must be considered when planning classroom management strategies. To ensure that the classroom is effectively managed, transferee teachers must be confident that the classroom management techniques they employ are appropriate for use with diverse student populations in the new school community (Goddard 2000; McCormick Shi, 1999). Besides being closely related to classroom management, culturally responsive practices also play a role in determining the way teachers assess students' learning (Irvine Armento, 2001). A culturally responsive teacher should understand the practices, purposes, and usage of various assessments and the importance of a balanced classroom assessment system to gauge diverse student learning (Stiggins, Arter, Chappuis, Chappuis, 2006). When teachers know how the students learn, assessing learners will be easier. Additionally, when teachers know the students, they will be able to design meaningful assessments and rubrics that can accurately measure quality. It is equally important that they be able to use assessment data to support

3.1.3. Established Social Networks—Adjusting to a new school's values, norms, and unwritten rules can be difficult. Transferee teachers might feel like outsiders and struggle to navigate the school's social dynamics. Transferee teachers are excluded by school dynamics and behavior that reflect, enforce, and reproduce prevailing social attitudes and values. School is a shared environment; everybody must have the right to participate, get adequate attention, express themselves, etc. But, whether the current school structure and social order facilitate such an atmosphere or not is a critical issue in the case of the transferee teachers. A suc-

cessful educational system may be impossible without strong relationships between teachers and administrators. The success of curriculum implementation largely depends on positive classroom experiences brought about by positive relationships with other teachers and administrators. In teacher-teacher and teacher-administrator relationships, according to Hamre and Pianta (2005), both parties bring a variety of goals, feelings, needs, and behavioral styles that will ultimately affect the quality of the relationships they develop and, in turn, influence the importance of their interactions in the school. They contend that strong interpersonal

individual student learning. The participant said that:
 "I am experiencing stress because I fail to properly manage my classroom and conduct interactive lessons through the use of the different strategies to my learners because I don't know my students well." (P3)

Furthermore, it is essential for the transferee teachers in their new school setting to prioritize getting to know their learners. Building trusting connections with the students improves classroom management, student engagement, and teaching effectiveness. Knowing students individually allows teachers to tailor their instruction to meet students' unique learning needs, styles, and preferences. This personalized approach has improved student academic outcomes (Hattie Timperley, 2007). In the same manner, understanding students' interests, backgrounds, and experiences helps teachers design relevant and engaging lessons. Engaged students are likelier to participate actively and retain information (Fredricks, Blumenfeld, Paris, 2004). It will create a positive teacher-student relationship, which contributes to effective classroom management. When students feel known and valued, they are likelier to follow classroom rules and cooperate with the teacher (Hamre, B Pianta, 2001).

cessful educational system may be impossible without strong relationships between teachers and administrators. The success of curriculum implementation largely depends on positive classroom experiences brought about by positive relationships with other teachers and administrators. In teacher-teacher and teacher-administrator relationships, according to Hamre and Pianta (2005), both parties bring a variety of goals, feelings, needs, and behavioral styles that will ultimately affect the quality of the relationships they develop and, in turn, influence the importance of their interactions in the school. They contend that strong interpersonal

bonds are essential for pupils to succeed in the classroom. According to Liberante (2012), as these relationships significantly impact students' academic performance and behavior, emphasis must be placed on their growth inside the school. This includes interactions between teachers and administrators. Additionally, without prior acquaintance, it can be difficult to interact with parents and adequately inform them about their child's development and school activities. Because parents have a significant impact on both the growth of their children and the success of the overall educational system, it is crucial to be familiar with them and sympathetic to their cultural practices. Building strong bonds with parents can result in positive parental involvement and support, which can have a big impact on a child's schooling. Therefore, transferee teachers must make every effort to create fruitful working connections with parents. Teachers cannot easily communicate with parents if they are new to them. As a result, parents cannot help their children with transitions, daily activities, and academics. These detrimental effects are not only related to a student's low academic performance but also impact the student's personal, social, and emotional development. Children who experience poor communication may feel more uncertain and unimportant in their envi-

ronment, which will not increase attendance. It cannot aid the learners in developing a passion for studying, which can be strengthened further with parental and academic assistance. Teachers can educate more effectively when they have positive relationships with parents and are familiar with their traits and culture. Transferee teachers can better adapt their instruction by learning more about the child's home environment, needs, and interests from their parents (Blumenfeld, 2004). It is important to note that adjusting to a new school environment can vary for each transferee teacher and may depend on factors such as the school's culture, the level of support received, the teacher's previous experiences, and personal characteristics. Flexibility, openness to change, and a positive attitude are key attributes that can facilitate a successful transition for transferee teachers. The experiences of the transferee teachers adjusting to the school community, lack of parental involvement, and developing meaningful lessons are the three themes that emerged from the participants' responses. Figure 3 shows the challenges of teachers teaching in rural schools and the emergence of four themes: cultural adjustment, student differences, excessive administrative tasks, and established social networks.

3.2. Adaptation Techniques for Success In Adjusting to the New School Community—Teachers encounter several challenging circumstances on a daily basis, especially in rural institutions. Since educators are the ones who subjectively assess the quality of the learning environment when they encounter challenges

and difficulties, providing them with support is essential for helping them deal with stressful situations. In 2005, Montgomery and Rupp had so many possibilities that it was imperative to have strategies for overcoming obstacles in order to provide high-quality teachings that all students must understand.

3.2.1. Develop Resilience—Some survey participants mentioned that building resilience was their coping strategy for dealing with the difficulties faced in rural schools. Teachers need

to be competent and adaptable in order to manage the many obstacles that today's classrooms present in ensuring that all students achieve academic achievement and meeting national ac-

Fig. 3. Emerging Themes on the Challenges of Teachers in Teaching in Rural Schools

countability criteria. The difficulties that teachers are currently facing are a persistent problem in the nation; teachers who lack these qualities may find it difficult to continue on the job. Teachers must possess resilience in order to handle these difficulties and keep up their effectiveness (Taylor, 2013). According to Bobek (2002), teachers must be resilient in order to handle difficult situations related to their line of work. Additionally, according to Bobek, resilient teachers are better equipped to assess challenging situations, identify ways to handle them, and put the right solutions into action. In order to develop resilience, Bobek advised giving people the tools they need, including strong adult relationships, a sense of personal responsibility, social and problem-solving skills, a sense of competence, expectations and goals, confidence, a sense of humor, and a sense of accomplishment. According to Bobek, having the ability to bounce back from setbacks is a key component of a great teacher. Despite the challenges as a new teacher in the community; cultural adjustment, student differences, and the feeling of isolation, the informants remained hopeful and optimistic. Their optimism yielded successful teaching careers and various

other positive experiences within the community in which they taught. Instead of focusing on adversity, the informants remained confident in their talents and abilities to positively impact children, connect to the teachers and the new community. Resilient teachers remain optimistic in spite of difficulties. Throughout their careers as teachers, each of the informants overcame obstacles. The informants were aware that they would face numerous challenges, such as a lack of resources for both learning and teaching, but they maintained their optimism and developed improvisational skills. Through their tireless efforts to deliver interesting and enjoyable lectures and place emphasis on the value of receiving an education, the informants' sense of hope and optimism was shared with their learners. The informants also mentioned how their experiences acted as a springboard for the growth of self-assurance, a sense of value, and healthy self-esteem. The informants also had confidence in their knowledge, skill, and capacity to instruct children in the school community. Teachers who are resilient are accountable for their own conduct (Walsh, 1998). Being a teacher may be a very dreary and solitary job. However, the informants relished the chance

to be independent and creative in addressing both the needs of their students and the parents. As they plan lessons for the classroom and connect with other teachers and administrators outside of it, they also take the initiative to make changes as necessary.

3.2.2. *Be a Critical Reflective Teacher*—Teacher development is a lifelong process, and no matter what stage a teacher is at, they all need opportunities to reflect, learn from, and teach one another (Taylor, Klein, and Abrams, 2014). Transferee teachers who are entering into a new community can often be an intimidating time. Especially if that transfer were to include a move to a much different sized school district. Whether it would be from a small district to a larger district or a large district to a smaller district, both would require an adjustment from the educator. According to Dinkelmann, Margolis, and Sikkenga (2006), when teachers begin new positions and begin to respond to the new context, they construct new knowledge for their work, and begin to form new identities. Therefore, be a reflective teacher. Regardless of the subject matter, from where you are, a skilled instructor pushes your mind to the next level, the next realization, the next insight, the next glimpse of knowledge. Effective educators consider and assess their own work, accomplishments, and shortcomings. Critical reflection is a critical attribute of good teachers. The ability to reflect on what, why, and how things are done and to adapt and refine practice is essential for successful teaching and learning (Rayford, 2010). Reflection is often defined as just thinking about something. Professional reflection is planned, intentional, and methodical. It is connected to learning theory and practice. Change can be realized through reflection, and there are various ways to do so (Fullan, 2005). Teachers can only grow by means of this reflective practice, according to York-Barr et al (2001). According to Schon (1987), reflective practice is an essential step in honing one’s artistic and craft in a certain field. For newly transferred teachers, he suggests reflective practice to evaluate how well their own practice aligns with that of other teachers in the new school community. Every stage of the teaching and learning process involves reflective practice. It shouldn’t only be a single event planned for a specific time of day. Effective educators constantly evaluate and modify their lessons. Nonetheless, it is not unusual for educators to reflect more deeply on the entire day after students have left. Teachers who are reflective ask themselves what aspects of their teaching methods still need improvement. They reflect carefully, methodically, and on a regular basis on what they teach. Stated differently, they develop into thoughtful professionals. Rethinking what and how we teach, the effect it has on students, and the overall effectiveness of the teaching and learning process can all be accomplished by reflecting on teaching practices. It’s a form of contemplation. It is also important to involve colleagues’ critical reflection; inviting colleagues to watch what their co-teachers do or engage in critical conversations with them helps transfer teachers notice aspects of practice that are usually hidden. Colleagues can suggest perspectives that newly transferred teachers might have missed in the new school community and responses to situations in which teachers feel clueless.

3.2.3. *Becoming Comfortable*—As teachers transition into a new district, they must work to get acquainted with their new work setting, which encompasses a large number of elements. They might have new or different expectations within the district, as well as from the admin-

istration or school board. Teachers might experience a change in the number of students or peers that they will be working with. They will also be adjusting to a new classroom where they must work to determine the appropriate seating arrangement, available class materials, different curriculum, and classroom management system. In response to these changes, transferee teachers use various strategies to regulate their reactions to promote adaptive responses and to minimize maladaptive responses. As an educator enters a new school district, transferee teachers expected to adapt to the curriculum and instructional and behavioral strategies implemented at that district. As educators adapt to these changes, they might often seek support from their new colleagues in order to ask questions, implement their recommendations, and in exchange of form new relationships. In 2005, Gagen and Bowie published an article that supported the notion that having friends and feeling comfortable in a work setting help in building self-esteem, which is a necessary condition for comfort and success. Maintaining a good relationship with colleagues is an important adjustment and consideration to be comfortable for transfer teachers. After all, they need advice on how to survive in school, or at least how to be accepted as part of the group. Transferee teachers reported that they try to immerse themselves in their workplace by doing extra, voluntary work requested by colleagues, particularly senior teachers, such as doing tasks related to information and communication technology or acting as a substitute teacher for when a senior teacher has to attend activities out of school. Another adjustment and consideration being a newly transferred teacher is maintaining a good relationship with parents as it is equally important. Many of the teachers reported that they often communicate with parents in a less formal and friendly setting. Teachers usually communicate with parents in an online chat plat-

form to inform students about their activities or behavior at school. For most of the teachers, this part of work is not as demanding as maintaining a relationship with the school principal. Additional adjustment and consideration of the personal needs for transferee teachers that include positive interpersonal relationships with colleagues; progressive collaborations with administrators, teachers, and parents; perceptions of open-door access to leadership; work-life balance; and positive school environment (Boyd et al., 2011; Curry Bickmore, 2012; Johnson et al., 2012). Adjusting to a new school community as a teacher involves both professional and personal aspects. By actively engaging with colleagues, students, and the broader school community, newly transferred teachers can contribute positively to the educational environment while building a sense of belonging and satisfaction in their new role. Teacher educators are in an ideal position to assist their students in achieving these objectives by modeling social justice and equity practices in the classroom during lessons. Modeling is viewed as one of the most effective means of learning any novel skill or acquiring knowledge (Bandura, 1986). When teacher educators model social justice and equity, their students are presented with practical examples of how these concepts could be practiced in an actual diverse classroom context. Therefore, modeling to pre-service teachers requires that teacher educators themselves have already made the cognitive shift to becoming agents of change. It would seem that DepEd agency can only occur if teacher educators sincerely confront their own prejudices, stereotypes, and biases against the backdrop of their own socialization, history, and lived experience as it manifests within a specific space and time. The article draws strongly on the narratives and reflections of teacher educators' lived experiences and personal socialization.

Fig. 4. Adaptation Techniques of Transferee Teachers in Adjusting to the School Community

3.3. *Educational Insights Learned from the Experiences of the Informants*—During the interview, we realized many things about the participants’ insights into their experiences adjusting to the new school community. One of the insights in the detailed discussion was how they face the challenges and the coping mechanisms used in teaching in rural schools. Teachers encounter particular difficulties that need for resiliency and flexibility. The informants maintained their optimism and hope despite the diffi-

culties associated with teaching owing to a lack of teaching resources, facilities, and equipment, role uncertainty and work overload caused by a teacher shortage, identifying engaging activities and lessons, and involving parents. Their optimism led to great teaching careers and numerous other beneficial experiences in the community where they taught. The informants chose not to focus on the difficulties they faced, choosing instead to believe in their skills and capacity to have a good influence on children.

3.3.1. *Cultivate Resilience*—Teachers in rural schools must be resilient since they encounter special difficulties. They learned to be creative as a result of these challenges. Rural school teachers may have fewer resources and may need to be inventive in their class delivery. This can entail utilizing technology, utilizing nearby resources, and customizing teaching methods to fit the requirements of the students. The participants also understood the importance

of interacting with parents and the local community to foster parental support for education and secure funding for their schools. Teachers can develop connections that benefit the school and the larger community by interacting with members of the community and local organizations. Moreover, they also developed their adaptability and flexibility. Teachers in rural schools may need to be flexible and adaptable due to unfavorable conditions including scarce

resources, low literacy, and a lot of obligations. In order to meet the demands of learners, one must be able to quickly pivot and modify strategies (Dwek, C.S. 2016). The participants also came to the realization that establishing a solid network of resources and exchanging best practices can assist teachers in overcoming obstacles and enhancing student results. Although there may be fewer professional options available to teachers in rural schools, they are nevertheless able to take advantage of opportunities for per-

sonal growth and development thanks to the close relationships they form with neighbors, coworkers, and other educational institutions. Resilient teachers persevere through challenges and setbacks, recognizing positive outcomes for their learners. Being creative and seeking support from parents, communities, organizations, other educational institutions, colleagues, and mentors can help maintain a positive attitude in the face of adversity.

3.3.2. *Taking Advantage of Teamwork—*

The participants disclosed that asking for help can be important, but that doing so can help them to get through difficulties and keep up their effectiveness as teachers. They understand that asking for help is a sign of strength. It is not simple, but accepting assistance and realizing that you can't do everything by yourself will help them to be more effective in their teaching endeavors. They also discussed how a solid support system may aid in overcoming obstacles and maintaining motivation. Both parents and members of the community are included in this. Teachers can benefit from the community's access to knowledge, resources, and financing. A smart way to support initiatives and projects in the classroom is to look for collaborations with neighborhood companies, non-profit groups, and governmental organizations. In the same manner, working together with parents can foster a sense of shared accountability for stu-

dents' academic success. By giving parents regular updates on their child's development, inviting them to parent-teacher conferences, and asking for their involvement in class activities and projects, teachers may create a strong support system for their students. Both independently and collectively, parents and schools have a key role in shaping and offering support for children's learning and growth. Each fulfills specific purposes and may meet various needs, and distinctions between them are significant. According to Fantuzzo, Tighe, and Childs (2000), family engagement is defined as parents making active, meaningful attempts to engage in home and school activities and behaviors that will help their children learn and develop. In this way, transferee teachers may feel comfortable with each other, leading to successful learning outcomes. According to decades of research (Barley Beesley, 2007), supportive relationships with families were among the most crucial elements for rural school performance.

3.3.3. *Equipping Educators with Skills and Knowledge—*To raise the standard of education and guarantee that students are receiving the greatest instruction possible, teachers must have the right tools. The interviewees expressed a need for professional development opportunities during the course of the conversation. Giv-

ing transferee teachers the chance to grow professionally can make them feel more confident in their new school community. Therefore, in order to stay current with industry best practices and current research, our teachers must have access to continual professional development. Additionally, they require access to sufficient

resources and assistance. It is crucial to arm the teachers with the tools and assistance they require in order for them to perform their jobs well in their new school environment. There may be opportunities for professional collaboration and mentoring, as well as access to technology, educational resources, and support personnel. The participants also said that they needed to be given autonomy and power over decisions. Giving instructors more freedom and control over their own decisions can make them feel more invested in and responsible for their profession. Greater job happiness, motivation, and innovation may result from this. Working cooperatively with their colleagues can help teachers share resources and ideas, solve problems, and create innovative teaching strategies. This is another method for advancing one's career. Teachers may have the chance to learn new methods, technology, and subject matter as a result. This can assist teachers in developing their subject-matter expertise and teaching techniques, which will improve the results for the students. Collaboration and teamwork are encouraged as a way to improve techniques and create a positive learning environment. Professional development for educators can help them become more reflective and self-aware. This may inspire educators to evaluate their methods and pinpoint

areas for improvement. Teachers might benefit from this by becoming more self-aware and understanding their strengths and flaws. Teachers are crucial to creating a strong and efficient educational system. By giving them the tools, resources, and support they require, we can ensure that students receive the greatest education possible and that transferee teachers feel empowered and satisfied in their work. The figure below shows the insights learned from the experiences of Transferee Teachers in Adjusting to the New School Community. Three themes emerge from the participants' responses: cultivating resilience, taking advantage of collaboration, and equipping teachers with skills and knowledge. These themes imply that adapting to change, building strong linkages, and seeking growth and development can improve student outcomes. Facilitating learning in an environment with a shortage of teachers, low literacy, and a lack of resources is challenging. However, when teachers remain committed with the help of the community and school, everything will work well. Figure 5 shows the educational insights learned from the informants' experiences and the emergence of three themes: cultivate resilience, Take Advantage of Collaboration, and Equip Educators with skills and knowledge.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter summarized the investigation and conclusions based on the study's findings. It also covered plans for teachers with previous experience working in rural schools, how the problems were solved, and what could be gained about education from the informants' experiences. This study aimed to analyze elementary school teachers' experiences working in rural schools and examine their approach to overcoming obstacles and imparting valuable lessons.

4.1. Findings—Teaching in rural schools was a bridge that connects students, parents, and the community, frequently using interactions so that the teachers can react to the difficult circumstances in a rural area. Teachers in rural settings gain pedagogical expertise, orga-

nizational skills, problem-solving abilities, the capacity to take on responsibility, the capacity to operate under pressure, and the capacity to be creative and innovative. The ability of teachers to solve interactive issues and work together is crucial to determining the school's

Fig. 5. Emerging Themes on Educational Insights Learned from the Experiences of the Informants

success. This study was created because public elementary school teachers were interested in learning about other educators' experiences in the district. They were concerned about their colleagues' struggles in a setting with few resources. Eight (10) teachers from various elementary schools in the Binugao District were interviewed. Their backgrounds ranged wildly. The following four themes emerged from elementary school transfer teachers' experiences teaching a new school community: Cultural Adjustment, Student Differences, and Established Social Networks. The teachers' strategies for dealing with the challenges of teaching in the new school community were a significant topic of discussion. Developing resilience, being a critically reflective teacher, and being comfortable are the three themes that emerged. Teachers' resiliency is related to teacher effectiveness and performance among pupils. More opportunities arise for teachers when they become critical reflective teachers, especially in

the new school community where teachers are not yet familiar with and become comfortable with the community to meet the requirements of the schools and further their professional growth. The last point was that by empowering teachers through professional development, teachers' responses to evolving, complicated, and demanding demands would result in self-improvement and competence and improve students' academic performance. Three themes also emerge from the participants' replies about the lessons learned from the experiences of rural school teachers, namely fostering resilience, harnessing teamwork, and equipping them with knowledge and skills. These themes imply that rural school teachers acquired the adaptability, creativity, and resourcefulness necessary to accomplish the objectives and develop students into internationally competitive individuals. The recurring themes were that resilient and well-connected teachers are essential for fulfilling the Department of Education's goals

of providing quality education. Furthermore, the education department may take strong action in using different teaching strategies. The department should address these issues to help

the teachers, the learners, and the rural community. The efforts of the teachers must be recognized and assist them for the success of the entire educational system.

4.2. Implications—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The challenges of teachers teaching in rural schools and the emergence of three themes: cultural adjustment, student differences, excessive administrative tasks, and established social networks. These were essential themes as the experiences of the transferee teachers to adapt to the new community were more challenging but important experiences for their personal development, like cultural adjustment, in which the first step to cultural adjustment was becoming aware of our own feelings and cultural patterns and how these affect our perceptions. Second, student differences were also a challenging factor. As new in the school community, it was important to make this adjustment to improve the delivery of teaching. Third, excessive administrative tasks must also be considered for personal adjustment to the new school assignment. As the new to the school, it was necessary to adjust the work assignment or task to acquire the trust of the co-teachers or community workers, and lastly, establish social networks in the new school assignment. Teachers can forge connections with their immediate friends and friends of friend's teachers, thereby building a robust network. Peer-to-peer networking is pivotal in enhancing online engagement and fortifying the teaching experience. The adaptation techniques teachers in rural schools use to deal with difficulties. The participants' responses revealed three themes: "Develop Resilience means teachers are coping with tough events. When something

bad happens, you still feel anger, grief, and pain. However, they could keep going, both physically and psychologically. Resilience was not about putting up with something tough or coping independently. Being a Critical Reflective Teacher means modeling the reflective process during class discussions by asking the kinds of questions that members of your discipline ask. Explicitly point out how you support a claim with evidence. Explain how you model the critical reflection process as you go through the process. Becoming comfortable means transferring teachers to a comfortable, cozy, snug, easy, and restful position, which means enjoying or providing a position of contentment and security. comfortable applies to anything that encourages serenity, well-being, complacency, and physical ease. started feeling comfortable in our new surroundings. The educational insights learned from the informants' experiences and the emergence of three themes: cultivate resilience and take Advantage of Collaboration, the researchers observed it as insight; collaboration facilitates the exchange of ideas and thoughts among team members who then weigh in on them with collective expertise. Collaboration in this sense acts as a force multiplier for innovative ideas and as checks and balances for ideas that cannot be executed or ones that need more thought put into them and Equip Educators with skills and knowledge it means that require knowledge of the unique skills that each child brings to the classroom in order to target instruction toward students' learning needs effectively.

4.3. Future Directions—

Despite their difficult circumstances, the Department of Education may provide full support to educators working in formal and informal settings, including public and private schools, whose main objective is to develop and uphold student-centered instruction through various teaching techniques. As a result, programs and trainings have been developed and made available to teachers. Teachers may be innovative in providing students with a high-quality education in a challenging environment since they are a key component of economic competitiveness. Teachers must use instructional techniques that foster critical thinking and life-long skills. The dissemination of education and training, collaboration, flexibility, and the evaluation of content and ability were all possible for teachers who use the resources at their access. It could help personal build professional abilities, including the capacity for independent research, the capacity for planning and organization, the capacity for time management, the capacity for problem-solving, the capacity for accountability, the capacity for working under duress, and the capacity for creativity and ingenuity. Combining educational skills with a greater understanding of a strategy's concept was crucial to successful use in rural settings. Furthermore, it was recommended that schools and districts provide time, resources, and needed support in response to the challenges encountered by teachers in rural schools. The school heads may emphasize the importance of these themes in the development of teachers, the community, and, most importantly, the learners. Teachers may always have a wide variety of teaching resources at their disposal in order to improve and update their pedagogical methods. The learners' well-being and development were teachers' top priorities. The best teachers enjoy the opportunity to learn and love to teach constantly. In order to consistently improve, teachers should make professional development a daily practice. Teachers need to be aware that the core of education is a

tight interaction between an informed, compassionate adult and a confident, driven child. The teachers should also understand that their most important role is to get to know each student to comprehend his or her unique needs, learning style, social and cultural background, interests, and abilities, especially in this new normal setup of education. Students may be taught the importance of educating themselves despite the obstacles. Additionally, teachers must provide activities that give students the freedom to decide what to learn, how to learn it, when, and where to study it. This adaptability was a crucial quality in the open learning process. The learners were also encouraged to go beyond the course requirements and learn things not covered in class to make their education more useful, advanced, and applicable. The government may identify the needs of the community – provide resources, and be able to come up with great solutions to elevate the burdens of the teachers and, at the same time, improve the quality of life that the community deserves. National and local government efforts should develop better technology, facilities, and equipment to improve educational programs. Advancement could be achieved through the development of intellectual capital. Moreover, a further study relevant to this implementation would uncover its impact on the Department of Education. The challenging circumstances of the community and rural teachers' needs should be taken into account when implementing the various solutions. This was because this would, in the end, be advantageous to both students and their educational institutions. The quality and appropriateness of the support provided to our teachers in the rural school, the supportiveness of the work environment, and the application of appropriate training policies and practices—rather than the quantity of training—determine how well training contributes to the continuous learning of the rural teachers. Finally, to fully understand the experiences that transferee teachers in the

new school community had and to further our knowledge of those experiences, similar qualitative research may be used across the nation to acquire a wider perspective and additional insights from different participants in this study.

5. References

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